

Point cloud matching-based augmented reality surgical navigation system for robot-assisted laparoscopic partial nephrectomy

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Abstract: Robot-assisted partial nephrectomy (RAPN) is the standard treatment for localized renal tumors. However, identifying buried tumors and determining resection margins remain challenging. This paper describes a novel augmented reality (AR) surgical navigation system that we are currently developing for RAPNs. The system generates an intra-abdominal point cloud from a stereo endoscopic camera video within approximately 1 second. Point cloud matching is performed between the intra-abdominal point cloud and the organ model of the patient created from preoperative computed tomography/magnetic resonance imaging images. We employ a two-stage matching approach: global matching using fast point feature histograms for initial alignment, followed by iterative closest point refinement for precise registration. The system successfully achieved registration with a root mean squared error of 1.546 mm for the clinical data testing. By overlaying these point clouds with the matching results, the system enables accurate and intuitive visualization of tumor locations and the positions of blood vessels and other critical structures, even when they are located inside or behind the organs. This AR navigation system has the potential to improve surgical precision, reduce positive margin rates, and preserve healthy renal tissue during RAPN.

Keywords: Surgical Support, Robot-Assisted Partial Nephrectomy, Augmented Reality, Point Cloud.

I. INTRODUCTION

The major surgical procedures for renal cancer include open, laparoscopic, and robot-assisted surgeries. Open surgery requires a large incision and places a significant strain on the patient. Laparoscopic surgery requires several small incisions in the abdomen through which an endoscope and forceps are inserted. Although postoperative recovery is faster than that in open surgery, the field of view of the surgeon is restricted, and the range of motion of instruments is limited; therefore, it requires a high level of technical skill. Robot-assisted surgery is a type of laparoscopic surgery that employs surgical robots. It has been widely used in recent years because of the superior vision provided by the endoscope and the high degree of freedom provided by the forceps.

The primary surgical approaches for renal cancer are nephrectomy and partial nephrectomy. Partial nephrectomy, which removes only the tumor from the kidney, is recommended because it preserves postoperative renal function. Partial nephrectomy performed using a surgical robot is known as robot-assisted partial nephrectomy (RAPN). Performing partial nephrectomy requires rapid identification of the tumor location and determination of the resection margin. The goal is not only to achieve complete resection of the

tumor but also to preserve renal function by minimizing damage to normal renal tissue. Damage to the normal renal tissue can lead to increased mortality and reduced renal function [1]. Ultrasound scanning is used to identify buried tumors [2]. However, this method cannot be used for deeply buried tumors, and accurately and intuitively determining the boundaries of the tumor is difficult.

Augmented reality (AR) has been used to develop intuitive surgical support systems. The effectiveness of AR surgical navigation in RAPN (laparoscopic radical prostatectomy) has been reported [3]. Offline registration between organ surface shapes and organ models has been proposed [4], AR surgical assistance using invasive markers placed on organ surfaces has been developed [5], and AR surgical assistance using monocular simultaneous localization and mapping with image feature points has been implemented [6]. It has also been reported that three-dimensional (3D) navigation reduces the risk of complications [7].

We are developing an AR-based RAPN support system that enables real-time processing during surgery using only an endoscopic camera video, which is a noninvasive device [8-10]. This system displays a 3D computer graphics (3DCG) model of the kidney, tumor, vessels, and ureter, overlaid with a point cloud of the

intra-abdominal space generated from stereo endoscopic camera videos. These 3DCG models were generated from preoperative computed tomography/magnetic resonance imaging images and represented using triangular polygons.

The system estimates the position and orientation of the organs by matching the vertices of the 3DCG models to the intra-abdominal point cloud. The 3DCG model is placed at the appropriate location in the intra-abdominal space by moving it according to the estimated position and orientation. Consequently, tumors and blood vessels located inside or behind the organs are visualized. Although the display is a two-dimensional monitor, both the tissue and point cloud models are 3D, and the viewpoint can be easily changed using a mouse, allowing for intuitive visualization of tumor and vessel locations. Furthermore, it provides a graphical user interface (GUI) that enables operations to start point cloud matching, select mouse operation modes, and adjust point cloud visibility and other settings.

Point cloud matching is typically applied to rigid objects. Therefore, few studies have attempted point cloud matching of deformable organs. The kidney, our subject, was relatively undeformed during surgery compared with other organs such as the heart, liver, or lungs. Furthermore, in RAPN, the kidney is not fully exposed, and point cloud matching is performed in situations with little deformation. Therefore, we consider the influence of deformation to be negligible.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. System Configuration

The system comprises two modules. One is an intra-abdominal point cloud generation system, which uses stereo endoscopic video as the input and outputs a point cloud. The other is a point cloud matching system, which takes two point clouds (intra-abdominal point cloud and 3DCG kidney model) as input and outputs the relative position and orientation between them. Each system is described as follows. The PC has an Intel Core i7-1165G7 CPU (2.8 [GHz]), 32 [GB] of memory, and an Intel Iris Xe GPU. The endoscopic video was captured using an AV.io HD, which converts HDMI to USB. The programming language used was Python (3.12.4), employing OpenCV-Python (4.10.0.82) for image processing, Open3D (0.19.0) for point cloud processing, and Tkinter (8.6.13) for the GUI. The da Vinci Xi surgical robot was operated at Kyoto University Hospital.

B. Intra-abdominal Shape Measurement System

Fig. 1 Intra-abdominal shape measurement system (upper left and right: color and depth images of the area used for point cloud matching; lower left: captured stereo endoscope image; lower right: depth image calculated from the stereo image)

Fig. 2 Example of a removed image except for the renal parenchyma and the tumor by dragging the mouse

Figure 1 shows the startup screen of the system. The stereo endoscope video imported into the PC was displayed at 30 [fps] in the lower-left corner of the screen. The stereo endoscope video was output side by side with a total resolution of 1920×1080 [pixels]. This image was separated into left and right images, rectified, and converted to a 960×540 [pixels] image with the proper aspect ratio. These images were used as source images for the depth calculation. The depth calculation is based on a semiglobal block-matching algorithm that utilizes StereoSGBM function of OpenCV. The internal and external parameters of the endoscopic camera were obtained using a chessboard pattern with `calibrateCamera` function of OpenCV.

Fig. 3 Example of target.ply. Left protrusion is tumor, and right is renal parenchyma.

Fig. 4 Example of whole.ply, which includes target.ply, surrounding tissues and fat around organs, along with the endoscope and forceps, providing the entire intra-abdominal view.

The depth calculation takes approximately 1 [s], and real-time processing was not possible. Therefore, a depth calculation was performed on a single video shot when the space key was pressed. The generated depth image is displayed in the lower-right corner of the screen. Some stereo processing parameters can be adjusted using slide bars at the top of the window. The left mouse button was dragged to paint the unnecessary areas to specify the area to be used for point cloud matching. Usually, the areas used for point cloud matching are the surfaces of the renal parenchyma and tumor, and the remainder of the area should be painted. Figure 2 shows the example of the filling areas other than the renal parenchyma and tumor. The system automatically deletes small blobs of less than a certain size to reduce painting time.

By pressing the 'r' key, two point cloud files are output in polygon file format (PLY) from the depth image. The first is the whole.ply file, which is a point cloud of the entire intra-abdominal cavity. The second is the target.ply, which is the point cloud used for point cloud matching. The following transformation was performed to generate a point cloud from the depth image:

$$\begin{pmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{d/B} \begin{pmatrix} u - c_x \\ v - c_y \\ f \end{pmatrix}$$

where X , Y , and Z are the coordinates of the 3D point cloud; d denotes the disparity; B denotes the baseline distance of the stereo camera; u and v are the coordinates of the depth image; c_x and c_y are the coordinates of the center of the optical axis; and f denotes the focal length. Examples of the generated point clouds are shown in Figures 3 and 4.

C. Point Cloud Matching System

Figure 5 shows the startup screen of the system. After specifying the point cloud file to be used for point cloud matching in the GUI (Figure 6), point cloud data are imported into the system by pressing the 'reload' button.

Global matching is performed based on fast point feature histograms feature using Open3D by pressing the 'run global' button. If the number of points in the point cloud data is excessively large, the system requires a long processing time. Therefore, the number of points was reduced to approximately one-thirtieth of that before processing.

The matching quality is evaluated using two metrics: fitness and inlier root mean squared error (RMSE). The fitness score represents the ratio of the inlier correspondences:

$$\text{fitness} = \frac{N_{\text{inlier}}}{N_{\text{source}}} \times 100$$

where N_{inlier} denotes the number of source points with corresponding target points within a specified distance threshold and N_{source} denotes the total number of points in the source point cloud. A higher fitness value indicates better coverage of the source point cloud. The inlier RMSE measures the alignment accuracy:

$$\text{inlier RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{\text{inlier}}} \sum_{i \in \text{inlier}} \|\mathbf{p}_i^{\text{source}} - \mathbf{p}_i^{\text{target}}\|^2}$$

where $\mathbf{p}_i^{\text{source}}$ and $\mathbf{p}_i^{\text{target}}$ are the corresponding points after transformation, and the summation is performed only over the inlier pairs. Lower RMSE values indicate better alignment precision.

The search process was executed repeatedly, initially storing ten candidates on the candidate list with no conditions. Further iterations of the search process add candidates to the list if the computed RMSE is less than

the minimum RMSE of the stored candidates. If the computed RMSE is smaller than the maximum RMSE of the stored candidates, the existing candidate is replaced. The search is terminated when a specified number of candidate replacements does not occur. In this study, the number of iterations was set to 20.

When the search was complete, the results with the minimum RMSE were displayed on the screen. The displayed results can be switched in the order of the candidates by pressing the 'next/previous candidate' button on the GUI. The doctor determines whether the displayed candidate has the correct positions and orientation and adopts the results. If no correct candidates are present, press the 'run global' button again to search for more candidates.

In reality, achieving a perfect match using global matching alone is difficult. Therefore, the optimal candidate from the global matching was used as the initial position and orientation, and Iterative Closest Point (ICP) matching was performed. This provides a more accurate alignment of the position and orientation. Clicking the 'run ICP' button on the GUI executes the ICP matching.

If global matching does not provide acceptable results after several attempts, the initial position and orientation can be specified manually using mouse operations. Additional features include buttons to 'increase/decrease point size,' allowing you to adjust the visibility of the point cloud. The 'switch whole' button enables toggling the display of whole.ply.

III. EXAMPLE OF EXECUTING THE POINT CLOUD MATCHING SYSTEM

The point cloud matching system (Figure 5) was tested using actual surgical data: an intra-abdominal point cloud (54613 points) and an organ model (16599 points, white). Visualization included tumor models (purple), artery models (red), and ureter models (yellow), which were not used for point cloud matching. Only the intra-abdominal and organ model point clouds were used for matching, with outlier removal and downsampling for stability and speed. After these processes, the numbers of intra-abdominal and model point clouds were 1415 and 1690, respectively. When global matching was performed between these point clouds, the search time was approximately 5 [s]. For reference, the search time for global matching without downsampling was approximately 30 [s]. The fitness and RMSE values of the ten candidates are listed in Table 1. In the clinical data testing, the system achieved a registration accuracy with an RMSE of 1.546 [mm].

Fig. 5 Main screen of the point cloud matching system. Left shows the intra-abdominal point cloud, right shows the organ model, with the renal parenchyma in white, the tumor in purple, the artery in red, and the ureter in yellow.

Fig. 6 GUI of the point cloud matching system

Table 1 Candidate list

candidate	fitness [%]	RMSE [mm]
1	10.970745	1.546477
2	11.037234	1.572818
3	11.436170	1.671608
4	7.978723	1.680080
5	7.646277	1.708167
6	12.034574	1.714311
7	7.712766	1.717409
8	12.101064	1.723602
9	12.101064	1.724624
10	7.845745	1.728096

Fig. 7 First candidate for global matching. As seen from the overlap between the organ and tumor of the 3D model and their positions in the intra-abdominal point cloud, the correct position and orientation were obtained. The second candidate was nearly the same as the first; therefore, no figure is shown here.

Fig. 8 Third candidate in the global matching. As the tumor protrusion overlaps with the organ protrusion, we observe that the result for the position and orientation of this candidate is incorrect.

The obtained candidates are displayed sequentially (Figures 7–9), and the first candidate has the correct position and orientation. Figure 10 shows the results of performing ICP matching from this state, and it shows that the matching is more precise. The time required for the ICP matching to converge was approximately 0.5 [s].

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper describes the development of point cloud matching-based AR navigation for robot-assisted laparoscopic partial nephrectomy. We demonstrated that the global matching method is feasible for position and orientation estimation. By providing precise guidance, this AR navigation system has the potential to improve

Fig. 9 The fourth candidate for global matching. It also gives incorrect position and orientation results.

Fig. 10 The result of *additional* ICP matching based on the position and orientation obtained by the first candidate of the global matching.

surgical accuracy, reduce positive margin rates, and preserve healthy renal tissue. Compared with the previous ICP-only matching system, we believe that the workload of the doctor is reduced, and the search time, including the operation of the doctor, is decreased. However, the point cloud to be matched must contain protruding features.

As a challenge for intra-abdominal shape measurement, we aim to implement semi-automated mask generation using segmentation deep learning models such as Segment Anything Model in the future. Regarding point cloud matching challenges, we plan to implement candidate narrowing by excluding evident errors. For instance, candidates for which the organ model is not embedded within the intra-abdominal point cloud were excluded. Furthermore, the optimal point cloud downsampling rate must be determined. Excessive down-sampling causes a loss of surface shape features, leading to estimation errors. Conversely, insufficient downsampling makes surface noise more influential and

increases the computation time. We are interested in finding a suitable down-sampling rate in the future.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Bertolo, H. Zargar, R. Autorino, C. Fiori, J. H. Kaouk, P. Russo, R. H. Thompson and F. Porpiglia. Estimated glomerular filtration rate, renal scan and volumetric assessment of the kidney before and after partial nephrectomy: a review of the current literature. *Minerva urologica e nefrologica*, 69(6), pp. 539-547, 2017.
- [2] B. Qin, H. Hu, Y. Lu, Y. Wang, Y. Yu, J. Zhang, Z. Zhang, H. Gao, Q. Wang and S. Wang. Intraoperative ultrasonography in laparoscopic partial nephrectomy for intrarenal tumors. *PLoS One*, 13(4), e0195911, 2018.
- [3] F. Esperto, F. Prata, A. Aufrán-Gómez, J. Rivas, M. Socarras, M. Marchioni, S. Albisinni, R. Cataldo, R. Scarpa and R. Papalia. New Technologies for Kidney Surgery Planning 3D, Impression, Augmented Reality 3D, Reconstruction: Current Realities and Expectations. *Current Urology Reports*, 22(7):35, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11934-021-01052-y>, 2021.
- [4] L. M. Su, B. P. Vagvolgyi, R. Agarwal, C. E. Reiley, R. H. Taylor and G. D. Hager. Augmented reality during robot-assisted laparoscopic partial nephrectomy: Toward real-time 3D-CT to stereoscopic video registration. *Urology*, vol. 73, no. 4, pp. 896-900, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.urology.2008.11.040>, 2009.
- [5] P. Edgcumbe, R. Singla, P. Pratt, C. Schneider, C. Y. Nguan and R. Rohling. Augmented reality imaging for robot-assisted partial nephrectomy surgery. in *Proceedings International Conference on Medical Imaging and Virtual Reality*, pp. 139-150, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-43775-0_13, 2016.
- [6] A. Hamada, A. Sawada, J. Kono, M. Koeda, K. Onishi, T. Kobayashi, T. Yamasaki, H. Noborio and O. Ogawa. The Current Status and Challenges in Augmented Reality Navigation System for Robot-Assisted Laparoscopic Partial Nephrectomy. *Springer, Human-Computer Interaction. Design and User Experience. HCII2020. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 12182, pp. 620-629, DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49062-1_42, 2020.
- [7] F. Piramide, K. Kowalewski, G. Cacciamani, I. R. Belenchon, M. Taratkin, U. Carbonara, M. Marchioni, R. D. Groote, S. Knipper, A. Pecoraro, F. Turri, P. Dell'Oglio, S. Puliatti, D. Amparore, G. Volpi, R. Campi, A. Larcher, A. Mottrie, A. Breda, A. Minervini and E. Checcucci. Three-dimensional model-assisted minimally invasive partial nephrectomy: a systematic review with meta-analysis of comparative studies. *European Urology Oncology*, 5(6), pp. 640-650, 2022.
- [8] M. Koeda, N. Maeda, A. Hamada, A. Sawada, T. Magaribuchi, O. Ogawa, K. Onishi and Hiroshi Noborio. Position and Orientation Registration of Intra-abdominal Point Cloud Generated from Stereo Endoscopic Images and Organ 3D Model Using Open3D. *Springer, Human-Computer Interaction, Technological Innovation, HCII 2022, Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 13303, pp. 52-65, 2022.
- [9] A. Sawada, T. Magaribuchi, A. Hamada, K. Masui, M. Koeda and T. Kamoto. Challenges to the development of a surgical support system for robot-assisted partial nephrectomy using highly versatile augmented reality. *The 39th Annual European Association of Urology Congress*, 85(1), S549, DOI: 10.1016/S0302-2838(24)00469-X, 2024.
- [10] T. Magaribuchi, M. Koeda, K. Masui, T. Kobayashi and A. Sawada. Accuracy Evaluation of AR Navigation in Partial Nephrectomy. *Springer, Human-Computer Interaction. HCII 2024. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 14686, pp. 194-202, 2024.